

INFLUENCE OF ATMOSPHERIC AGING FACTORS ON STRAIN-STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF IMPACT-RESISTANT POLYSTYRENE

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ABSTRACT

Experimentally studied is an effect of atmospheric aging on strength-strain characteristics of ABC plastic. Data analysis of two-layer model has been made on the basis of failure mechanics accounting the peculiarities of material aging. Obtained is a displacement of brittle-tough transition to the region of positive temperature dependence of aged specimens. Linearization under aging of material brittle-tough peculiarities is demonstrated. The problem of worsening of products' operational characteristics made of composites in the process of aging under cold climatic conditions is not well studied yet /1/. An analysis of experimental data on atmospheric effect /1-4/ has shown that the changes of impact plastics are mostly sufficient. Climatic factors effect on these materials is mainly resulted in surface damage when physical-chemical changes are limited by the near-surface region of the specimen or product with linear dimension of 10-100 μm . Studied are ABC-2020 plastic and its weather-proof modification (ABC-2020-32). Standard, incised and model specimens (the latter are called specimen-models and covered with the artificial layer) have been taken for the experiment. An incision of 1 mm deep is sharpened by the razor blade to a depth of 0.4 mm. Specimen-models are manufactured by means of spreading of brittle layer made on the basis of epoxy resin 150 μm thick on the specimens' lateral surface. The specimens have been exposed under climatic conditions of Yakutsk and tested on strength in the conditions of uniaxial tension at a speed of 5 mm/min, within the temperature range of 123-333 K. The mechanism of failure changes under the atmospheric effect (Fig. 1). In the range of low temperature the specimens under exposure have been damaged before the state of yielding onset *. Typical transition is obtained at exposure period increase (Fig. 1, curves 3,4). Over the temperature of transition specimen's strength becomes practically insensible to surface cracking and, in the limits of experiment accuracy, is identical to reference material. The peculiarities mentioned of failure mechanism allows to describe a specimen as a two-layer model consisting of a layer damaged by the aging and a layer of basic material. While testing on tension a surface layer is used for the cracks initiation and basic material resists to these cracks extension. The characteristics of fractures initiated are considered to be a complex multifactor function of the exposition period. Inhibition characteristics of the model under discussion do not change during the period of atmospheric effect. Data for the specimens incised (Fig. 2) show that brittle-tough transition being similar to one stated above (Fig. 1, curves 3,4; Fig. 2, curves 6,7) for

Data of fractographic analysis show that failure is caused by the quick unstable growth of the crack being initiated from the surface layer failed by the aging.

the material aged is typical for the reference material (Fig. 2, curves 2,3)

Fig. 1 Temperature dependence of strength of the ABC-2020 material specimens upon the period of exposition. 1 - initial, $\sigma = \sigma_T$; 2 - 1 month; 3 - 3 months; 4 - 18 months (hatched designations correspond to the state of yielding onset, $\sigma = \sigma_T$).

Fig. 2 Temperature dependences ; 1 - ABC 2020-32; 2 - ABC 2020 with incision; 3 - ABC 2020-32 with incision; 4 - ABC 2020-32 model; 5 - ABC 2020-32 model; 6 - ABC 2020-6 months under aging; 7 - ABC 2020-32-6 months of aging;

Displacement of this transition under long-term exposition is explained by sharp increase of speed of material deformation at the end of the crack initiated by the brittle surface layer. Due to failure mechanics relationships [5], it is possible to evaluate the dimension of plastic range at the end of the crack on the basis of data on strength of reference specimen with the incision in the temperature range below the transition temperature (Fig. 2, curve 2). For the reference specimen with incision the radius of plastic zone is 10^{-5} m for the state of plain stress and 10^{-6} m for the state of plane stress at $T=193$ K. Taking into account the specimen geometrical dimensions (thickness $B = 3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m), fracture size being initiated by the surface layer ($h = 10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$ m) and also data of fractographic analysis of fracture surface, the phenomenon of aged specimen failure is possible to be explained from the point of linear mechanics of fracture. For the practical purposes the limiting value of displacement (Fig. 2, curves 4,5) is supposed to be determined in the process of model experiment using reference specimens artificially covered by the brittle surface layer. The capability of surface layer to initiate cracks within wide range of stresses to be applied to the specimen under tension is explained by the considerable inhomogeneity of the layer strength characteristics increasing during long-term exposition. In the case of limiting situations possible is such degree of surface layer damage which is contributing to the completion of crack formation in it at relatively low level of tensile stresses. Under this condition a brittle surface layer is not considered to be capable to initiate a fracture resulting in the specimen failure even at the temperatures being considerably below the temperature of

brittle-tough transition T_c . Stated is the fact that strength characteristics have become the same as the ones of the reference specimens. The effect described has been experimentally observed under long-term artificial ultraviolet irradiation of high density polyethylene /2/. Also studied have been changes in the mechanism of materials' strain in the process of atmospheric effect. The experimental results /3/ show that for the reference materials typical is the non-linearity of visco-elastic condition. To evaluate the degree of non-linearity used is the technique suggested in /6/. Time dependence of the stress modified is represented in double logarithmic coordinates (Fig. 3). A shift along the time axis corresponds to the coefficient of speed-time reduction. A diagram of the modified stress demonstrates that in the process of aging a non-linearity is decreasing monotonously. Under low temperatures a decrease is more sharp. At low strains visco-elastic characteristics have been linearized after one month of exposition (Fig. 3,4).

Fig. 3 Modified stress of ABC-2020 at $T=303K$ and different periods of exposition: a-reference specimens; b-1 month; c- 2 months; d- 12 months.

Fig. 4 Speed (a,b) and time (c,d,) dependences of the speed-reduction coefficient of ABC-2020 at the temperatures of 303 (a,b) and 243 K (c,d).

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